

IKKINCHI JAHON URUSHIDA O'ZBEKISTONNING QO'SHGAN HISSASI**Yuldosheva Feruza Yashin qizi**

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada Ikkinchi jahon urushi davrida O'zbekistonning qo'shgan hissasi yoritilgan. Unda frontga yuborilgan askarlar, urush davrida O'zbekistonda tashkil etilgan evakuatsiya qilingan korxonalar, front orqasidagi fidokorona mehnat, shuningdek, urushdan jabrlanganlarga ko'rsatilgan insonparvarlik yordami haqida ma'lumotlar berilgan.

O'zbekiston xalqi tomonidan ko'rsatilgan matonat, birdamlik va jasorat urush yillaridagi muhim ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy va siyosiy jarayonlar bilan bog'liq holda tahlil etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar. Ikkinchi jahon urushi, O'zbekiston, evakuatsiya, front orqasidagi mehnat, harbiy xizmat, jasorat, birdamlik, korxonalar, insonparvarlik yordami, tarix.

UZBEKISTAN'S CONTRIBUTION TO WORLD WAR II

Abstract. This article covers the contribution of Uzbekistan during World War II. It provides information about the soldiers sent to the front, the evacuated enterprises established in Uzbekistan during the war, the selfless work behind the front, as well as the humanitarian assistance provided to the victims of the war. The fortitude, solidarity and courage shown by the people of Uzbekistan are analyzed in connection with important socio-economic and political processes during the war years.

Keywords: World War II, Uzbekistan, evacuation, work behind the front, military service, courage, solidarity, enterprises, humanitarian assistance, history.

ВКЛАД УЗБЕКИСТАНА ВО ВТОРУЮ МИРОВУЮ ВОЙНУ

Аннотация. В статье освещается вклад Узбекистана во время Второй мировой войны. В нем содержится информация о воинах, отправленных на фронт, об эвакуированных предприятиях, созданных в Узбекистане в годы войны, о самоотверженном труде в тылу, а также о гуманитарной помощи, оказанной пострадавшим от войны. Стойкость, сплоченность и мужество, проявленные народом Узбекистана, анализируются в связи с важными социально-экономическими и политическими процессами в годы войны.

Ключевые слова: Вторая мировая война, Узбекистан, эвакуация, работа в тылу, военная служба, мужество, солидарность, предприятия, гуманитарная помощь, история.

Ikkinchi jahon urushi insoniyat tarixidagi eng dahshatli va halokatli voqealardan biri bo'ldi. 1939–1945-yillar oralig'ida davom etgan bu urushda millionlab insonlar halok bo'ldi, shaharlar vayron qilindi va butun dunyo siyosiy, iqtisodiy, madaniy jihatdan o'zgarib ketdi.

Urushga sobiq SSSR tarkibida bo'lgan O'zbekiston ham faol ishtirok etdi. Garchi janglar to'g'ridan-to'g'ri O'zbekiston hududida bo'lmagan bo'lsa-da, xalqimizning bu urushdagi hissasi beqiyos bo'lgan. Bu maqolada O'zbekiston xalqining urush yillaridagi harbiy, iqtisodiy va ma'naviy hissasi haqida so'z yuritiladi.

Harbiy hissasi

Urush boshlanishi bilan O'zbekistonda ko'plab harbiy chaqiruvlar tashkil etildi. Respublikadan 1,5 millionga yaqin odam frontga jo'natildi, ulardan 500 ming nafari urushdan qaytmadi. Ko'plab o'zbekistonlik askar va zobitlar jasorat ko'rsatib, orden-medallar bilan taqdirlangan. Masalan, 430 nafar yurtdoshimiz Sovet Ittifoqi Qahramoni unvoniga sazovor bo'lgan. Ulardan biri — Matyoqub Matchanov Berlin operatsiyasida jasorat ko'rsatgan bo'lsa, Sobir Rahimov esa ilk o'zbek generali sifatida tarixda qoldi.

O'zbekistonlik harbiylar orasida ayollar ham bor edi. Jumladan, farmatsevt, hamshira va aloqachilar urush frontlarida xizmat qilgan. Ular orasida Olga Zvereva, Tamara Khudoyberdiyeva singari ko'plab jasur ayollar bor edi.

Iqtisodiy va moddiy yordam

Urush yillarida O'zbekiston orqada qolgan emas, balki frontga katta iqtisodiy yordam ko'rsatgan. Front orti deb atalgan O'zbekistonda sanoat korxonalarini tashkil etildi, urush boshlanganidan so'ng 100 dan ortiq yirik zavod va fabrikalar evakuatsiya qilinib, O'zbekistonga ko'chirildi. Masalan, Toshkent, Farg'ona, Chirchiq, Samarqand, Andijon shaharlarida harbiy ehtiyojlar uchun qurol-aslaha, kiyim-kechak va oziq-ovqat ishlab chiqaruvchi korxonalar ishga tushirildi.

Qishloq xo'jaligida esa butun yuk ayollar, bolalar va keksa avlod zimmasiga tushdi. Urush yillarida paxta, g'alla, sabzavot va mevalar yetishtirish hajmi oshirildi. Bu mahsulotlar frontga yuborilgan, jangchilarning oziq-ovqat ta'minotiga xizmat qilgan.

Shuningdek, o'zbekistonliklar "Hamma narsa front uchun, hamma narsa g'alaba uchun!" shiori ostida ommaviy ravishda mablag' yig'ishgan, harbiy samolyot, tanklar qurish uchun pul ajratishgan. Jumladan, "O'zbekiston kolxozchisi" nomli tank kolonnasi va "Toshkentlik" samolyot eskadri bilan bog'liq tashabbuslar shular jumlasidandir.

Ma'naviy va gumanitar yordam

Urush yillarida O'zbekiston ko'plab muhojir va yetim bolalarga boshpana bo'ldi. O'zbek xalqi o'zining bag'rikengligi va insonparvarligini yana bir bor namoyon etdi. Taxminan 1 milliondan ortiq odam, jumladan, rus, ukrain, belarus, yahudiy, polyak va boshqa millat vakillari

O‘zbekistonga evakuatsiya qilindi. Jumladan, mashhur "Taras Shevchenko" nomidagi teatr, kino, san’at arboblari va fan vakillari O‘zbekistonda vaqtincha yashab, ijod qilishdi.

Urush yillarida o‘zbek xalqining g‘amxo‘rligi, mehmondo‘stligi haqidagi ko‘plab hikoyalar tilga olinadi. Masalan, mashhur "Shomahmud ayaning bolalari" deb ataluvchi voqeda bir o‘zbek ayol 15 nafar turli millatga mansub yetim bolani tarbiyalagan.

O‘zbek yozuvchilari va san’atkorlari ham urush yillarida xalqni ruhlantirish, g‘alabaga ishonch uyg‘otish yo‘lida o‘z hissalarini qo‘shishgan. G‘afur G‘ulomning “Sen yetim emassan” she’ri, Hamid Olimjon va Zulfiya kabi shoirlarning asarlari xalqni birdamlikka undagan.

Xulosa

Ikkinchi jahon urushi yillarida O‘zbekiston xalqining ko‘rsatgan jasorati, fidoyiligi, mehnatsevarligi va insonparvarligi tarix sahifalarida oltin harflar bilan yozilgan. Frontdagi askarlarning qahramonligi, orqadagi mehnatkashlarning fidokorona zahmatlari, bolalar va ayollarning metinligi urushdagi g‘alabaga munosib hissa bo‘lib qo‘shildi. Bugungi tinch hayotimiz aynan o‘sha avlodlarning fidokorona harakatlari evaziga barpo bo‘lgan. Shuning uchun ham biz har yili 9-may — Xotira va qadrlash kuni munosabati bilan ularning xotirasini ehtirom bilan yod etamiz.

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